

EVALUATION OF ADHESION STRENGTH OF PLASMA-SPRAYED COATING FOR COMPLEX LOADING BY TENSILE TEST

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Abstract A method is developed for evaluating the adhesion strength of coating on substrate using flat tensile sample. The developed method takes into account the complex stress states that occurs in the vicinity of the free edge of the coating during its delamination. Considering the problem of coating on a substrate by theory of elasticity, it is shown that the delamination of the coating is caused by the combined effect of the interface shear stresses and the normal peeling stresses. An approach accounting for the combined effect is proposed and it is evaluated for determining the adhesion strength of plasma-sprayed Co-Cr alloy coatings of various thicknesses. Numerical calculations of the tensile samples with the coatings using the finite element method showed that the stresses in the vicinity of the free edges of the coating initiate failure. The combined stress approach to adhesion strength was found to be more accurate and reliable than the common shear-lag approach.

Keywords: *adhesion, coatings, edge effects, stress intensity factors, finite element analysis (FEA), uniaxial loading.*

1. Introduction

To study the causes, type, and nature of the failure of structural elements with coating, it is necessary to consider their local stress states during service [1- 4]. Tests on coated samples have shown that delamination of the coating from the substrate begins from the edge of the coating even when there is no initial crack in the adhesive contact plane [5]. The theory of elasticity solution to the problem of bonded bi-materials shows that in the edge zone the stress state is singular with a combination of tensile and shear stresses. It is therefore expected that the delamination of coatings is likely to initiate near the edge zone.

The study of the singularity of stress fields was initiated in [6], where plates of various configurations made of homogeneous and composite materials were analyzed. For wedges made of two different materials the stress singularity problem was considered in [7-10].

There are many publications on the analysis of stress states in the vicinity of the free edge of the coating by both analytical and numerical methods [11; 12]. For analytical solutions, the perturbation method [13, 14] and the method of complex potentials [15, 16] were used. The occurrence of cracks between the substrate and the coating in the vicinity of the free edge was also considered in [17].

The purpose of the article is to analyze the stress state in coated samples under substrate tension and to develop a technique for determining the adhesion strength of coatings, which considers the complex stress state in the vicinity of the free edge of the coating. In the following, a substrate-coating system subjected to tension is analyzed by the theory of elasticity. The stress solution is applied to one specific material system. Considering the failure mechanisms involved in delamination of coating, it is argued that

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an approach to adhesion strength must consider the combined effect of the peel stress and shear stress.

2. Analytical method

2.1 Analysis of the substrate-coating system

Each component of the system is an elastic and isotropic material. Calculations will be carried out for a sample with a coating schematically shown in Fig. 1. The following designations have been introduced: $L, 2H$ – the length and thickness of the substrate, respectively; l, h are the length and thickness of the coating where ($l < L; h < 2H; h < l$).

Fig. 1. Scheme of the coated sample

It is assumed that the magnitude of stresses developing in the direction perpendicular to the action of tensile forces can be neglected. Then the stress state in the coating and substrate is plane and coincides with that developed in their section by a plane perpendicular to the free edge of the coating, which is in contact with the substrate.

In calculations, the polar coordinate system located in this section has been used, with the origin at the point O of the intersection of the secant plane with the mentioned edge of the coating and the polar axis (axis Oz) emanating from the selected origin in the direction of the line of intersection of the secant plane with the plane of coating-substrate interface (Fig. 2). Then the position of any point of the sample (substrate and coating) is determined by the distance from the origin of coordinates and the angle θ between the radius vector r and the z axis. The coating is located in the area $0 < \theta \leq \theta^c, 0 < r < \frac{h}{\sin\theta}$. In addition, the substrate is located in the area $\pi < \theta < 2\pi, 0 < r < -\frac{H}{\sin\theta}$. The free surfaces of the coating and the substrate may be subject to the action of normal and shear forces. On the contact surface, the conditions of coupling of stress fields and displacements are applied under the condition of absence of slipping.

Fig. 2. Element of the coated sample in the polar coordinate system (area A from Fig. 1)

Elasticity moduli E and shear G , as well as Poisson's ratios denote respectively E_c, G_c, μ_c and E_s, G_s, μ_s . Here and below, the indices c refer to the coating and refer s to the substrate.

The purpose of solving the problem is to estimate the stresses in the vicinity of the free edge of the coating on the surface of its contact with the substrate. It is proposed to

estimate these stresses based on the analysis of the nature of the singularity of the stress state in the vicinity of point O.

It is assumed that the thicknesses of the coating and the substrate are much greater than the radius of the singularity zone R , which is in the vicinity of the point O. Therefore, the following inequality is satisfied $0 < R \ll h \ll H$.

Based on this assumption, it is considered that the distribution of stresses and strains in the vicinity of the point O in actual coatings and the substrate, which have finite dimensions, asymptotically (as the point of their definition approaches the point O) coincide with the corresponding stresses and strains in the vicinity of the same point O, which is the top of an infinite flat wedge with a given opening angle θ^c , which is in a state of rigid contact with the rectilinear boundary of a semi-infinite plane.

With this in consideration, the wedge and the half-plane modelling the coating and the substrate, respectively, are in the following areas:

area c ($0 < r < +\infty; 0 < \theta < \theta^c$),

area s ($0 < r < +\infty; \pi < \theta < 2\pi$).

Their contact is along the beam $0 < r < +\infty; \theta = 0$.

In the model under consideration, the action of external forces can be carried out along the beam $0 < r < +\infty; 0 < \theta < \theta^c$

$$\sigma_n = \sigma_\theta^c; \quad \sigma_\tau = \tau_{r\theta}^c \quad (1)$$

where σ_n – external normal stress, σ_τ – external shear stress (along the direction of polar radius change r).

At the same time, it is assumed (because of the earlier assumption of a plane stress state), that there are no other external shear stresses:

$$\text{along the beam } 0 < r < +\infty; \theta = \pi: \quad \sigma_n = \sigma_{sn}^\pi, \sigma_\tau = \sigma_{s\tau}^\pi; \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } r = \infty; 0 < \theta < \theta^c: \quad \sigma_n = \sigma_{cn}^\infty, \sigma_\tau = \sigma_{c\tau}^\infty; \quad (3)$$

$$\text{and } r = \infty; \pi < \theta < 2\pi: \quad \sigma_n = \sigma_{sn}^\infty, \sigma_\tau = \sigma_{s\tau}^\infty \quad (4)$$

In addition, the bodies c and s act on each other along the line $0 < r < +\infty; \theta = 0$, on which the following conditions of conjugation of stresses and displacements are satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{r\theta}^c &= \tau_{r\theta}^s, & \theta &= 0 \\ \tau_\theta^c &= \tau_\theta^s, & \theta &= 0 \\ u^c &= u^s, & \theta &= 0 \\ v^c &= v^s, & \theta &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Stress tensor components σ_r , σ_θ and $\tau_{r\theta}$ expressed through a Airy function $\varphi(r, \theta)$ [17]. For each of the contacting bodies c and s it is determined respectively by the equations

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right)^2 \varphi_c(r, \theta) = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \right)^2 \varphi_s(r, \theta) = 0 \quad (7)$$

To correctly set the boundary value in the case under consideration means that together with the system of Eqs. (6), (7) it is necessary to set eight, and only sixteen boundary conditions and conjugation conditions for each of the coordinates. However, only twelve conditions are written above. As a result (in the case of solving a mathematical problem by the method of separation of variables), there are no four conditions for finding sixteen integration constants. This implies the non-uniqueness of the solution.

The reason for this is, that the concept of correctness implies not only the correspondence between the order of the system being solved and the number of boundary conditions, but also the need to use the correct coordinate system when solving. The coordinate system in the selected area of the plane is called correct if only two intersecting coordinate lines pass through each point of this area. This provides a one-to-one correspondence between the set of points in the region and the set of pairs of numbers that are their coordinates. In problem considered, this definition is violated at the pole of the polar system, point 0. At all other points of the plane and their vicinity, the polar system is correct.

In order to achieve the correct formulation of the problem of the action of a concentrated force on the wedge vertex in the correct coordinate system, when solving the problem, the vertex in the polar system is “cut off” by an arc of radius $r = \varepsilon$ and load the wedge with a distributed load along the cut. By doing so, the system of boundary conditions for both the area c and the area s can be supplemented with four more conditions:

$$\text{where} \quad r = \varepsilon; 0 < \theta < \theta^c: \quad \sigma_n = \sigma_c^\varepsilon, \quad \sigma_\tau = \sigma_c^\varepsilon; \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and} \quad r = \varepsilon; \pi < \theta < 2\pi: \quad \sigma_n = \sigma_s^\varepsilon, \quad \sigma_\tau = \sigma_s^\varepsilon \quad (9)$$

In this case, the stresses in Eqs. (8) and (9) are unknown. They are induced by other known stresses and are to be determined. Nevertheless, the boundary value problem is set taking into account Eqs. (8) and (9), the corresponding particular solutions are found, a linear combination containing sixteen unknown integration constants is composed, and based on Eqs. (1)–(5), (8) and (9) an inhomogeneous system of sixteen linear algebraic equations is written.

Due to the unknown stresses in Eqs. (8) and (9), these equations can only be used to determine these stresses at known integration constants. Thus, it is necessary to ensure, that all sixteen constants are found from twelve equations.

It is assumed that all sixteen boundary conditions are defined. The general solution of the system of equations for the unknown sixteen constants of integration is the sum of the general solution of the homogeneous system of linear algebraic equations, obtained from the original system by equating the boundary conditions to zero, and the particular solution of the inhomogeneous system [19].

If all conditions are given, then the main determinant of the system is not equal to zero, and the homogeneous system has a zero solution. It is necessary that four conditions be a consequence of the other twelve. Hence, four equations are a consequence of twelve others. This is possible if all determinants of the thirteenth and higher orders, composed of elements of the main determinant, are equal. This can be achieved by introducing uncertain parameters into functions that are particular solutions of differential equations (6), (7), the values of which are determined by equating the corresponding determinants to zero.

After this is done, a homogeneous system of twelve linear algebraic equations for sixteen unknowns (four are discarded due to their linear dependence on the remaining twelve) is considered. The twelve constants are expressed in terms of four, which can take on arbitrary values. Further the values of these four constants are set to zero, instead of a homogeneous system of twelve equations, the same system is considered, but with known right-hand sides - known boundary conditions. As a result, a particular solution of the inhomogeneous system for the integration constants is found. Summing it up with the previously obtained general solution of a homogeneous system, a general solution of an inhomogeneous system containing four unknown constants is obtained. They could be determined by including the third body Q (absolutely rigid cylinder) with radius ε , inserted at the apex of the wedge and half-space into a container obtained from them by “cutting out” regions of the same radius as mentioned above. Then this inclusion would be a transmitter of forces and displacements along the lines from the wedge to the half-plane and vice versa:

$$r = \infty; 0 < \theta < \theta^c \quad \text{and} \quad r = \infty; \pi < \theta < 2\pi.$$

Since in the general case it is very difficult to solve this problem mathematically and make a detailed analysis of it, a number of simplifications were made. To solve this problem, the following has been done. Since the nature of the singularity is primarily of interest, and not the exact distribution of stresses corresponding to the given system of boundary conditions (1)–(4), the functions $\varphi_c(r, \theta)$ and $\varphi_s(r, \theta)$ it was decided to choose in the following simplified form:

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_c(r, \theta) &= \rho_c(r) = f_c(\theta) \\ \varphi_s(r, \theta) &= \rho_s(r) = f_s(\theta)\end{aligned}\tag{10}$$

Functions $\rho_c(r)$ and $\rho_s(r)$ in this entry are considered known and specially selected in such a way as to solve the problem. Functions $f_c(\theta)$ and $f_s(\theta)$ are determined as a result of solving differential equations, which are obtained by substituting functions (10) into Eqs. (6) and (7). With this substitution, it turns out that the functions $\rho_c(r)$ and $\rho_s(r)$ it is convenient to choose in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_c(r) &= r^{\lambda_c+1}; \\ \rho_s(r)\rho_s(r) &= r^{\lambda_s+1},\end{aligned}$$

where λ_c, λ_s – unknown parameters, the values of which will be determined later.

In this case, the number of integration constants decreases, as well as the number of boundary conditions and conjugation conditions decrease too. There are eight integration constants: C_1, \dots, C_8 . Boundary conditions and conjugation conditions are not written for the values $r = \varepsilon$ and $r = \infty$. There remain eight boundary conditions and conjugation conditions. Boundary conditions at $r = \infty; 0 < \theta < \theta^c$ and $r = \infty; \pi < \theta < 2\pi$, and also when $r = \infty; 0 < \theta < \theta^c$, and $r = \infty; \pi < \theta < 2\pi$ disappear. Parameters λ_c, λ_s are chosen such that $r = \infty; 0 < \theta < \theta^c$ and $r = \infty; \pi < \theta < 2\pi$, and the stress tends to zero. This condition is considered as a boundary condition. To simplify the search for values λ_c and λ_s they are equated: $\lambda_c = \lambda_s = \lambda$. As a result, following the general scheme of reasoning outlined above, to determine the value λ it is necessary to equate to zero only one main determinant.

General solutions of Eqs. (6) and (7) are found in the form

$$\phi_s = r^{\lambda+1} f_s(\theta)\tag{11}$$

where

$$f_s(\theta) = C_1 \sin(\lambda + 1) \theta + C_2 \cos(\lambda + 1) \theta + C_3 \sin(\lambda - 1) \theta + C_4 \cos(\lambda - 1) \theta\tag{12}$$

and

$$\phi_c = r^{\lambda+1} f_c(\theta)\tag{13}$$

where

$$f_c(\theta) = C_5 \sin(\lambda + 1) \theta + C_6 \cos(\lambda + 1) \theta + C_7 \sin(\lambda - 1) \theta + C_8 \cos(\lambda - 1) \theta\tag{14}$$

(C_1, \dots, C_8 – arbitrary constants).

Stress and displacement components are determined by the formulas [17]:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_r^s &= r^{\lambda-1} [f_s''(\theta) + (\lambda + 1)f_s'(\theta)] \\ \sigma_\theta^s &= r^{\lambda-1} [\lambda(\lambda + 1)f_s(\theta)] \\ \tau_{r\theta}^s &= -r^{\lambda-1} \lambda f_s'(\theta)\end{aligned}\tag{15}$$

$$2G_s u^s = r^\lambda [-(\lambda + 1)f_s(\theta) + (1 + \mu_s)^{-1} g_s'(\theta)]$$

$$2G_s u v^s = r^\lambda [-f_s'(\theta) + (1 + \mu_s)^{-1} g_s'(\theta)]$$

where

$$g_s(\theta) = 4(\lambda - 1)^{-1}[C_3 \cos(\lambda - 1)\theta + C_4 \sin(\lambda - 1)\theta]$$

and

$$\sigma_r^c = r^{\lambda-1}[f_c''(\theta) + (\lambda + 1)f_c'(\theta)]; \sigma_\theta^c = r^{\lambda-1}[\lambda(\lambda + 1)f_c(\theta)];$$

$$\tau_{r\theta}^c = -r^{\lambda-1}\lambda f_c'(\theta)$$

(16)

$$2G_c u^c = r^\lambda[-(\lambda + 1)f_c(\theta) + (1 + \mu_c)^{-1}g_c'(\theta)]$$

$$2G_c v^c = r^\lambda[-f_c'(\theta) + (1 + \mu_c)^{-1}(\lambda - 1)g_c(\theta)]$$

where

$$g_c(\theta) = 4(\lambda - 1)^{-1}[C_7 \cos(\lambda - 1)\theta + C_8 \sin(\lambda - 1)\theta]$$

At $r \rightarrow 0$ the stress components are proportional to $r^{\lambda-1}$, displacement components $\sim r^\lambda$, where $\lambda-1$ – stress field singularity order,

$$\sigma_r^s; \sigma_r^c; \sigma_{r\theta}^s \sim r^{\lambda-1};$$

$$\sigma_r^c; \sigma_r^s; \sigma_{r\theta}^c \sim r^{\lambda-1};$$

(17)

$$u^s, v^s, u^c, v^c \sim r^\lambda$$

For this case, the displacements correspond to a plane stress state. A tensile load is applied to the substrate. Other surfaces are unloaded. Thus, the following boundary conditions and continuity conditions are obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{r\theta}^c &= \tau_{r\theta}^s & \theta &= 0 \\ \sigma_\theta^c &= \sigma_\theta^s & \theta &= 0 \\ \sigma_\theta^s &= 0 & \theta &= -\pi \\ \tau_{r\theta}^s &= 0 & \theta &= -\pi \\ \tau_{r\theta}^c &= 0 & \theta &= \frac{\pi}{2} \\ \sigma_\theta^c &= 0 & \theta &= \frac{\pi}{2} \\ u^c &= u^s & \theta &= 0 \\ v^c &= v^s & \theta &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

After substituting the boundary conditions (18) into Eqs. (15), (16), a system of eight linear equations with respect to the constants C_1, \dots, C_8 is obtained:

$$\sum_{i=1}^8 C_i \cdot a_{ij}(\lambda) = 0 \quad (19)$$

where $a_{ij}(\lambda)$ – coefficients at unknown arbitrary constants are presented $i = 1, \dots, 8; j = 1, \dots, 8$ (Table.1).

Existence of non-trivial values C_1, \dots, C_8 is possible if

$$|\Delta(\lambda)| = 0 \quad (20)$$

where $|\Delta(\lambda)|$ – 8th order determinant, composed of coefficients at C_1, \dots, C_8 .

Equating the determinant to zero, the characteristic equation with respect to λ is obtained. The study of this characteristic equation is of interest in studying the behaviour of stresses and displacements. Of particular interest, from the point of view of the singularity, is the region of small values $r(r \rightarrow 0)$.

Table 1. Coefficients $\mathbf{a}_{ij}(\lambda)$ systems of equations (19)

a_{ij}	i			
	1	2	3	4
1	$-(\lambda+1)$	0	$-(\lambda-1)$	0
2	0	-1	0	-1
3	$-\sin(\pi(\lambda+1))$	$\cos(\pi(\lambda+1))$	$-\sin(\pi(\lambda-1))$	$\cos(\pi(\lambda-1))$
4	$(\lambda+1) \times \cos(\pi(\lambda+1))$	$(\lambda+1) \times \sin(\pi(\lambda+1))$	$(\lambda-1)\cos(\pi(\lambda-1))$	$(\lambda-1) \times \sin(\pi(\lambda-1))$
5	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0
	0	$-(\lambda+1)$	0	$-(\lambda+1) + 4/(1+\mu_s)$
	$-(\lambda+1)$	0	$-(\lambda-1) + 4/(1+\mu_s)$	0
7	$(\lambda+1)$	0	$(\lambda-1)$	0
8	0	1	0	1
9	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0
11	$(\lambda+1) \times \cos(\pi/2(\lambda+1))$	$-(\lambda+1) \times \sin(\pi/2(\lambda+1))$	$(\lambda-1) \times \cos(\pi/2(\lambda-1))$	$-(\lambda-1) \times \sin(\pi/2(\lambda-1))$
12	$\sin(\pi/2(\lambda+1))$	$\cos(\pi/2(\lambda+1))$	$\sin(\pi/2(\lambda-1))$	$\cos(\pi/2(\lambda-1))$
13	0	$(\lambda+1)G_s/G_c$	0	$-G_s/G_c \times (4/(1+\mu_c) - (\lambda+1))$
14	$(\lambda+1)G_s/G_c$	0	$-G_s/G_c \times (4/(1+\mu_c) - (\lambda-1))$	0

The characteristic equation (20) has an infinite number of real and complex solutions. Restricting the solution domain by the inequality $0 < \text{Re}(\lambda) < 1$, the order of singularity λ for stress and displacement fields is obtained. The order of singularity of stress fields depends only on the elastic characteristics and configuration of the substrate coating system and does not depend on the load conditions.

2.2 Determination of stresses in a coated sample

The stress components in the polar coordinate system are determined from the expressions:

$$\sigma_r^s = \frac{1}{r^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \phi_s}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial r} \quad (21)$$

$$\sigma_\theta^s = \frac{\partial^2 \phi_s}{\partial r^2} \quad (22)$$

$$\tau_{r\theta}^s = -\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial r} \right) \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma_r^c = \frac{1}{r^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \phi_c}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_c}{\partial r} \quad (24)$$

$$\sigma_\theta^c = \frac{\partial^2 \phi_c}{\partial r^2} \quad (25)$$

$$\tau_{r\theta}^c = -\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi_c}{\partial r} \right) \quad (26)$$

For coated sample ($\theta^c = \pi/2$; $\theta^s = -\pi$) (Fig. 1) stress in the area of adhesive contact, i.e. at $\theta = 0$ can be written in the form:

$$\sigma_r^c(r, 0) = \frac{K}{r^{1-\lambda}} \cdot (-\lambda(\lambda + 1)C_1 - \lambda(\lambda - 3)C_4) \quad (27)$$

$$\sigma_r^s(r, 0) = \frac{K}{r^{1-\lambda}} \cdot (-\lambda(\lambda + 1)C_6 - \lambda(\lambda - 3)C_8) \quad (28)$$

$$\sigma_\theta^c(r, 0) = \frac{K}{r^{1-\lambda}} \cdot (\lambda(\lambda + 1)(C_2 + C_4)) \quad (29)$$

$$\sigma_\theta^s(r, 0) = \frac{K}{r^{1-\lambda}} \cdot (\lambda(\lambda + 1)(C_6 + C_8)) \quad (30)$$

$$\tau_{r\theta}^c(r, 0) = \frac{K}{r^{1-\lambda}} \cdot (\lambda(\lambda + 1)C_1 + \lambda(\lambda - 1)C_3) \quad (31)$$

$$\tau_{r\theta}^s(r, 0) = \frac{K}{r^{1-\lambda}} \cdot (\lambda(\lambda + 1)C_5 + \lambda(\lambda - 1)C_7) \quad (32)$$

where K – stress intensity factor.

In order to determine the coefficients C_1 – C_8 from the system of eight linear equations (19), C_8 is set equal to 1, after which the remaining coefficients C_1, \dots, C_7 are determined.

3. Experimental Methods and Materials

Cobalt-chromium alloy coating [19; 20] with thickness 90, 100 and 160 μm plasma sprayed onto a stainless-steel substrate (1Kh18N9 stainless steel containing 0.9% C, 16.7% Cr, 7.8% Ni, 0.37% Si, and 1.47% Mn) with 1,5 mm thickness. The coating was plasma-sprayed onto the metal substrate in part to form the free edge of the coating. (Fig. 1). The sample and features of coating deposition were described in detail earlier in [22]. The elasticity characteristics of the substrate and coating were determined by stretching the sample with a coating according to the technique given in [23].

4. Results and Discussion

The elasticity characteristics of the substrate and coating, obtained after tensile tests of coated samples according to the technique given in [23], are shown in Table 2. For this substrate coating system, the singularity index calculated based on the solution of the characteristic equation (20) is $\lambda = 0.5687$.

Table 2. Elastic characteristics of the substrate and coating

	Material	Elastic modulus E, GPa	Poisson's ratio μ
Substrate	1Kh18N9	199	0.28
Coating	Co-Cr alloy	70	0.3

Coefficients C_1, \dots, C_8 of the substrate-coating system under consideration, obtained for the case of a plane stress state, are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Coefficients $C_1 - C_8$ for coating on stainless steel 1Kh18N9 substrate

C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
-0.5359	0.2348	0.2924	1.3456	-0.6522	0.5804	-0.1307	1

The value of K depends on the geometric dimensions of the sample and the load applied to the sample (Fig. 1). Previous studies have shown that the critical stress intensity K_{cr} for a plasma-sprayed coating of Co-Cr alloy, depending on the thickness, varies from 0.88 to 1.34 $\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.43}$ [21].

According to the formula (31):

$$f_C(\lambda, 0) = (\lambda(\lambda + 1)(C_2 + C_4)) = 1.41$$

Taking into account the coefficient f_c , the value of K can be determined from the formula:

$$K = \frac{K_{cr}}{f_C(\lambda, 0)}$$

Thus, critical stress intensity K_1 caused by normal peel stresses is calculated by the formula:

$$K_1 = K \cdot (\lambda(\lambda + 1)(C_2 + C_4))$$

The critical stress intensity K_2 caused by shear stresses, can be calculated by the formula:

$$K_2 = K \cdot (\lambda(\lambda + 1)C_1 + \lambda(\lambda - 1)C_3)$$

Results of determining critical stress intensity K_1 and K_2 are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of determining critical stress intensity K_1 and K_2

Coating thickness h , μm	Stress singularity index λ	K	K_1	K_2	Dimension [MPa·m ^{1-λ]}
90	0.5687	0.95	1.34	–	MPa·m ^{0.43}
100		0.67	0.94	–	
160		0.62	0.88	–	
				0.34	

An analysis of the stress state in the vicinity of the free edge of the coating obtained using the ANSYS software shows that the maximum normal peel stresses σ_y are greater than the shear stresses τ at the substrate coating interface. As an example, the fields of normal and shear stresses are given, which cause delamination of a coating with a thickness of 160 μm (Fig. 3). For this case, the maximum normal peel stresses σ_y are 350 MPa, while the maximum shear stresses τ is 152 MPa. That is, the maximum normal peel stresses σ_y is more than twice the maximum shear stresses τ . This is also confirmed by the stress distribution plots in logarithmic coordinates (Fig. 4). As the singularity point is approached, the normal peel stresses increase more rapidly than the shear stresses. This fact must be taken into account when evaluating the adhesion strength of coatings, since in most known methods, when using a sample of the configuration shown in Fig. 1, only shear stresses in the substrate-coating interface are determined [24; 25; 26; 27; 28]. It should be noted that when testing samples with coatings for bending, the difference between the maximum normal and shear stresses in the vicinity of the free edge of the coating is not so large [29].

(a)

(b)

Fig.3. Stresses in a sample coated with of 160 μm a thickness coating: (a) normal peel stress, (b) shear stress

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Stress distribution in the substrate coating interface during delamination of coatings of various thicknesses: (a) 90 μm , (b) 100 μm , (c) 160 μm

Accounting for the ratio of maximum stresses in the vicinity of the free edge makes it possible to more accurately determine the adhesion characteristics of coatings. In addition, it should be noted, that the resistance to the action of normal and shear stresses at the substrate-coating interface is different both for plasma-sprayed coatings [30; 31; 32] and for coatings, obtained using other deposition technologies [33; 34]. Most techniques for determining adhesion strength for plasma sprayed coatings use peel or shear tests of the coating from the bonded metal counter-body.

If, under the action of shear stresses in the substrate-coating interface, the delamination resistance of the coating is mainly affected by the roughness of the substrate [35; 36], then under the action of normal peel stresses, the fracture mechanism is more complex [37]. So, for example, according to Weiss, the mechanisms of adhesion can be divided into three groups: (1) mechanical interlocking, (2) physical bonding and (3) chemical bonding [38]. And the influence of these groups on the fracture process is different.

Therefore, the advantage of the proposed technique for determining the adhesion strength of coatings is a more accurate consideration of the complex stress state that occurs in the substrate-coating interface.

Conclusions

The geometric dimensions of the sample and the magnitude of the external load affect the value of K (stress intensity factor) and do not affect the ratio of normal to shear stresses in the area of the free edge of the coatings, which remains constant. When stretching samples with a coating that has a free edge (Fig. 1), it is impossible to carry out delamination of the coating only due to shearing according to mode I (i.e., when $\tau_{r\theta}^c(r, 0) = \tau_{r\theta}^s(r, 0) = 0$) or delamination of the coating only due to shear according to mode II (i.e. at $\sigma_{\theta}^c(r, 0) = 0$). The research shows, that the distribution of stresses in the region of the free edge of the coating has a complex character. It is noted, that the delamination of a plasma-sprayed coating during tensile tests of samples is affected not only by shear stresses, but also by normal peel stresses. Therefore, when determining the adhesion strength, it is necessary to take into account this complex stress state in the coated sample.

The study shows that the proposed approach for adhesion strength evaluation is a reproducible and correct tool compared to techniques that are based on shear-lag model. The developed technique was applied to plasma-sprayed Co-Cr alloy coatings. Numerical analysis of the stress state in the vicinity of the free edge of the coating showed that the

delamination of the coating is affected by both normal peel stresses and shear stresses in the plane of the coating-substrate interface.

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Abbreviations

c	Refer to the coating;
C_1, \dots, C_8	Arbitrary constants;
E	Elasticity modulus;
f	Coefficient;
G	Shear modulus;
H	Half thickness of substrate;
h	Thickness of substrate;
K	Stress intensity factor;
K_{cr}	Critical stress intensity;
K_1	Critical stress intensity caused by normal peel stresses;
K_2	Critical stress intensity caused by shear stresses;
L	Length of substrate;
l	Length of coating;
r	Radius vector;
s	Refer to the substrate;
u	Displacement;
θ	Angle between the radius vector r and the z axis substrate;
μ	Poisson's ratio;
σ	Normal stress;
σ_n	External normal stress;
σ_τ	External shear stress;
τ	Shear stress;
ε	Radius;
v	Displacement;
λ	Order of singularity.

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Fig. 2. Scheme of the coated sample

Fig. 2. Element of the coated sample in the polar coordinate system (area A from Fig. 1)

Fig.3. Stresses in a sample coated with of 160 μm a thickness coating: (a) normal peel stress, (b) shear stress

Fig. 4. Stress distribution in the substrate coating interface during delamination of coatings of various thicknesses: (a) 90 μm , (b) 100 μm , (c) 160 μm